

INTERCATEGORY CONVERSION IN FRENCH

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we can see the analysis of the phenomenon of intercategory conversion of words in the French language with the help of the literature of some scientists and writers. They also talked about the mutual transfer of word groups, their types, and their meanings. In addition, the effect of suffixes on words and the difficulties they cause are also mentioned, and in addition to this, the phenomenon of conversion from verb to noun, from noun to verb and again within the adjective group in modern French and the formation of words. The syntactic function of the interrogative in the sentence has been specially addressed.

Key words: conversion, word formation, intercategory communication, grammatical task, nominative addition, functional addition.

One of the urgent problems in today's linguistics is the phenomenon of word formation, which is still a controversial debate that has not lost its complexity. Word formation is the creation of new lexical units based on the possibilities and materials available in the language. Word formation serves to continuously enrich the vocabulary of the language. Nominative, i.e., functional migration of words is a widespread phenomenon in the language, which involves the transfer of a lexeme belonging to one word group to the function of another word group. But this process is not just an exchange, but is considered one of the methods of new word formation: Conversion is the formation of a new word by transferring a lexical base to another paradigm of word formation.

In modern French, there are the following types of migration between word groups:

1. Noun (Substantivation),
2. Adjective (adj) (Adjective),
3. Numbering (Numerilization),
4. Pronominalization,
5. Approach (Adverbialization),
6. Verbalization (Verbalization),
7. Description (Essivation)
8. Interjection (interjection),
9. Modalization
10. Promotion
11. Binding, (Reliure)
12. Loading (Particulation).

When directly analyzing the migration of word groups in any language, there are two inseparable aspects of this issue: the migration of that word group to other word groups and the migration of other word groups to this word group. should not be avoided, because the

value of both types of migration is equal in the implementation of the language unit in the speech and the realization of the communication between word groups. When words move from one category to another, the grammatical essence and partial meaning of this word changes. The transition of a noun to an adjective is also such a phenomenon.

In general, in the French language, words with the meaning of sign-property come before the noun and before the verb, and perform the function of concretizing their meaning. In this case, they have the same grammatical form of the word. In the sources, the presence of words like "good" ("bien" or "bon/ne") before the verb is considered as a conversion (migration) event. It should be taken as a possibility of quality lexemes in speech

In some dictionaries, it is possible to witness that a number of adjectives like "good" are given as adverbs. It seems that adjectives in the dictionary have the ability to express the sign of action like adverbs, that is, the semantic development of adjectives allows them to exchange syntactic functions. This situation, which has the nature of being able to combine with a verb, is probably the reason why adjectives denoting characteristics are interpreted as adverbs in the dictionary.

In French, when creating words through the conversion method, as in other languages, this situation can be found more often in the noun group. There are several types of this method, and the reason for their different types is the types of noun phrases. The conversion method, taking into account the above, is a unique word formation method and plays an important role in this productive method through these aspects.

So in French, conversion only applies to nouns, verbs and adjectives. Therefore, it can be observed in six cases: noun>adjective, noun>verb, adjective>noun, adjective>verb, verb>noun, and verb>adjective. However, Kerleroux and Namer confirmed that the verb>adjective relationship was not developed in French and observed five different conversion phenomena that exist in French. These are:

nom > adjectif :orangen>orangea,

rosen>rosea nom > verbe :colle>coller,

fouine>fouiner adjectif > nom

bleua>bleun, calma>calmen adjectif > verbe :fixe>fixer, rouge>rougir verbe > nom:marcher>marche, oublier>oubli

However, the past participle and adjective do not cause conversion. For example:

☒ blesséparpassé>blessés,

☒ ralentirparpassé>ralentis,

☒ disparuparpassé>disparus

At first glance, the following situation seems like a conversion event, but it is not a conversion. Namer and Kerleroux evaluate this event as far from conversion and consider this process simply as a change in the effect of suffixes.

This process also creates some difficulties in the analysis of suffixes in adjectives. For example, it is somewhat difficult to determine the exact common suffixes for the following adjectives:blessé, ralenti, disparu, découvert.

On the other hand, the phonological form of these adjectives always resembles the adjective of the verb. Thus, adjectives can be analyzed as adjectives of verbs. However, if these adjectives are analyzed as conversion, they change from the past participle of the verb.

At this point, I think it is appropriate to pay attention to Aronoff's theory, which is based on the phonological field of the base, which is applied in accordance with the morphological rule,

regardless of the presence or absence of an affix. Thus, the verb *marcher* or the noun formed by changing the noun *marche* is similar to the root of the verb base. Some adjectives seem to be used as adverbs. For example:

bas (parler bas), bref (parler bref), chaud (tenir chaud), cher (payer cher), court (couper court), double (voir double), droit (marcher droit), dru (pousser dru), dur (frapper dur),	ferme (discuter ferme), fort (frapper fort), haut (parler haut), juste (penser juste), net (couper net), pareil (penser pareil), petit (écrire petit), vrai (parler vrai) faux (chanter faux)
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If we talk about the conversion process in other word groups, in the French language, along with the adjective word group, the conversion process is often found in the noun and verb word groups. The famous linguist Delphine Tribout conducted scientific research on this topic and created many scientific works. In particular, his manual "Les conversions de nom à verbe et de verbe à nom en français" (conversion in French from noun to verb and from verb to noun) can be a clear proof of our opinion.

In his work, he defines conversion as follows:

"La conversion est un procédé morphologique de formation d'unités lexicales, illustrée par les exemples en (1), au même titre que les procédés affixaux comme, par exemple, la suffixation en -iser formant des verbes dénominaux (cf. (2a)) et la suffixation en-age formant des noms déverbaux (cf. (2b)).

- (1) a. agrafe > agraffer
- b. marcher > marche
- (2) a. caramel > caraméliser
- b. laver > lavage

The use of this method of word formation in modern French is widely popular, and in this case the grammatical function of the word changes, that is, the syntactic function it performs also changes. In addition, in this case, the question asked to him will change to another one. For example:

- a. Jean a fait tomber une agrafe.
- b. Jean agrafe les feuilles ensemble.

In the first example, the word "agrafe" is a noun group, and its syntactic function in the sentence is COD, i.e. complement. If we want to ask a question about this part of the sentence, we use *qu'est-ce que*. In the second example, the word "agrafe" is a verb.

In short, creating a new word in the language, putting it into context and revealing the importance of the meaning understood by that word is one of the biggest tasks of lexicology. The French dictionary is rich in information and instructions through the phenomenon of conversion.

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